

Central Pain Syndrome

+ Definition, causes, presentation, diagnosis
& treatment

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**DEFINITION – WHAT IS
CENTRAL PAIN?**

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

- + Central pain syndrome (or central pain) is a neurological condition caused by EITHER damage to OR dysfunction of the central nervous system (CNS). The CNS includes the brain, brainstem , and spinal cord⁽¹⁾.
- + This syndrome can be caused by:
 - Stroke
 - Multiple sclerosis
 - Tumors
 - Epilepsy
 - Brain or spinal cord trauma
 - Parkinson's disease

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

Ascending pathways

- + Spinothalamic tract (sensory tract)
- + Divisions: Anterior spinothalamic tract, lateral spinothalamic tract, spinoreticular tract, spinotectal tract
- + 1st order neuron – neurons within the DRG
- + 2nd order neuron – substantia gelatinosa of Rolando, nucleus proprius – send afferents to thalamus via Lissauer's tract
- + 3rd order neuron – thalamic nuclei – send afferents to primary sensory cortex (postcentral gyrus) via corona radiata

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

Ascending pathways

- + Mechanisms: transduction, transmission and modulation.
- + The pain sensory neurons detect pain.
- + The neurons send signals as action potentials to other neurons.
- + The neurons release excitatory neurotransmitters glutamate, which depolarizes cells, and substance P, which promotes inflammation & pain.
- + The signal reaches the DRG and then in the spinothalamic tract and upward to the somatosensory cortex which perceives pain.

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

Ascending pathways

Spinothalamic tract

Spinothalamic tract

Figure 1 Ascending pain pathways. DRG dorsal root ganglion, PAG periaqueductal grey matter

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

Descending *pathways*

- + Modulation...
- + Signal from the ascending pathway reaches the somatosensory cortex.
- + The descending pain modulation pathway is triggered.
- + Neuronal inhibition occurs in the periaqueductal gray (PAG), then relayed down to the rostral ventral medulla (RVM).
- + The neurons in the RVM then send a signal down the spinal cord to release endogenous opioids at neuronal synapses at multiple points in the peripheral nervous system to prevent these pain signaling neurons from sending action potentials (2).

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

Descending *pathways*

+ Additionally, these endogenous opioids are released in parts of the dorsal horn of the spinal cord to further block ascending pain transmission signals (3).

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

Descending pathways

DEFINITION – Central Pain Syndrome

- + “Central sensitization of pain occurs when the patient's nervous system is persistently in a high-activity state.”
- + “This state decreases sensitivity to fire action potentials...the central nervous system responds as if there have been many painful stimuli” (4).
- + Many action potentials crowd in, firing at the same time—causing spatial summation.

CAUSES – Central Pain Syndrome

CAUSES – Central Pain Syndrome

- + Brief etiology:
- + Central pain is often regarded as neuropathic pain, localized to the CNS...a dysfunction of the nervous system versus an adaptive change seen with musculoskeletal (nociceptive) pain [4].
- + The purpose of pain is protection - to restrict harm. So, it only is it not protective, but it is also actually a maladaptive response that can occur in patients following a stroke or with multiple sclerosis [4].
- + Challenge the old misconception that CPS is rare. Based on general population figures. 5-15% of the general population, most of whom have fibromyalgia [4].
But ...CPS can occur in chronic rheumatological and musculoskeletal disorders as well (acute pain → chronic pain and becomes centralized).

CAUSES – Central Pain Syndrome

Some numbers to consider:

- 10 to 40% of patients with rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, osteoarthritis, spondyloarthritis, and lupus [4].
- 30% of patients with multiple sclerosis. [5]
- Post stroke pain = **8-46%**, some quote **8-55%** [6][7]. Central post stroke pain, associated with thalamic strokes AND damage to the spinothalamic pathway, is debilitating.

Let the Numbers
Speak for
Themselves

CAUSES – Central Pain Syndrome

A point worth noting!

- All cases of thalamic pain syndrome are a kind of central post-stroke pain and fall under that broad umbrella. However, not all cases of central post-stroke pain are thalamic in nature.
- A more accurate description of central post-stroke would be pain secondary to injury of the spinothalamic tract. [10]

**Let the Numbers
Speak for
Themselves**

CAUSES – Central Pain Syndrome

The numbers

- ▶ Cancer is an odd ball. **37–64%** of cancer patients [8]. Cancer crosses over CNS to PNS or from PNS to CNS, causing destruction along its path. Mixed central (neuropathic)-peripheral (somatic/nociceptive) pain.
- ▶ TBI: **48%** per Ofek and Defrin in 2007 versus **69%** of patients with mild TBI in 2015 [9].

Presentation – Central Pain

- + The pain is variably distributed, may affect a large portion of the body or may be more restricted to specific areas, such as hands or feet.
- + The pain is typically constant, may be moderate to severe in intensity, and is often made worse by:
 1. Touch
 2. Movement
 3. Emotions
 4. Temperature changes, usually cold
- + The pain can present with varied pain sensations, the most major being burning. Along with the burning may be:
 1. Feelings of "pins and needles"
 2. Pressing, lacerating, or aching pain
 3. Sharp stabbing pain

Presentation – Central Pain

- + People may also have numbness in the areas affected by the pain.
- + The burning and loss of touch sensations are usually most severe on the distant parts of the body, such as the feet or hands^[4].
- + Central pain syndrome often begins shortly after the injury or damage that caused it. It may also be delayed by months or even years, especially if it is related to post-stroke pain ^[4].

Presentation – Central Pain (central sensitization)

Patients with central pain have developed central sensitization.

Central sensitization involves the following:

1. changes in the brain occur from repeated nerve stimulation, committed to experiential memory. A stimulus that is painful will cause the body to experience pain hypersensitivity.

- 2 Central sensitization appears in two forms – allodynia and hyperalgesia.

Allodynia makes people feel pain from things that usually don't hurt, while hyperalgesia amplifies the pain caused by a painful stimuli.

3. Central sensitization can change patterns in cerebral processing.

Diagnosis – Central Pain

- + The diagnosis for central pain is clinical.
- + Labs like a CBC, ESR, CRP, TSH, and CK, are typically normal [4].
- + Rheumatologic markers such as RF and ANA are unnecessary unless an autoimmune disorder is suspected [4].
- + fMRI detects connectivity between multiple regions of the brain.

Treatment – Central Pain

- + Tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs)
- + Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs)
- + Anticonvulsants

There is **strong** evidence for using TCAs such as amitriptyline, SNRIs such as duloxetine or venlafaxine, and anticonvulsants pregabalin and gabapentin. In addition, there is **moderate** evidence for using tramadol or selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs). [4]

Other AEDs sometimes used in treatment of pain include carbamazepine (Tegretol) and topiramate (Topamax).

Treatment – Central Pain

A holistic approach is necessary for the treatment of centralized pain.

- + Physical therapy
- + Occupational therapy
- + Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)
- + Modalities - traction, manual manipulation, ultrasonographic therapy, hot or cold applications, positioning, desensitizing therapy, stretching exercises, and transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS).

Images – Public domain

Treatment – Central Pain

Proprioceptive feedback mechanisms

- Wearing a prosthesis reduces phantom pain in patients with amputations, especially in UE amputation cases.
- Mirror therapy – in amputee care.

Images – Public domain

Treatment – Central Pain

Motor cortex stimulation (MCS) and deep brain stimulation (DBS) are effective treatment modalities for patients with refractory pain, **centralized pain**, and peripheral neuropathy. [11]

Implantation of stimulating ECoG probe into intrasulcal M1.

- (A) Double-faced silicone electrode array.
- (B) Photograph of the left fronto-parietal lobes before probe implantation. The CS was dissected from surface to bottom. PreCG, precentral gyrus; PostCG, postcentral gyrus; A, anterior; D, dorsal; asterisk, surgical cotton.
- (C) High-magnification view of the CS with inserted electrode array.
- (D) Low-magnification view of the CS following implantation of the probe. White arrowheads indicate the bridging veins preserved carefully.

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Treatment – Central Pain

+ Most often, Deep brain stimulation (DBS) and motor cortex stimulation (MCS) are reserved for severe, complex, disabling, and medically refractory syndromes after less invasive approaches have been tried. [11]

Case 1

- + 62-year-old female with MS who presenting with “burning fiery pain” in her legs. She couldn’t sleep at night and couldn’t tolerate performing any kind of therapy.
- + Awful allodynia and hyperalgesia.
- + Her PCP had tried hydrocodone, and anxiolytics (Lorazepam). Tried many treatments: herbal, OTC, etc. Developed multiple allergies.
- + Discontinued opioid and anxiolytic. Started her on SSRI in the am and a TCA in pm. De-sensitization therapy.
- + Doing well. Stable.

Case 2

- + 40-year-old male s/p hemorrhagic stroke (due to uncontrolled HTN) presenting with stabbing “forks of excruciating pain” in his left leg.
- + Had allodynia.
- + Tried on numerous agents: narcotics, and Cymbalta and Topamax. Developing “poor cognition.”
- + Tapered him off the narcotics and Topamax. Added Gabapentin. Therapy.
- + Doing well. Stable.

Case 3

- + 59-year-old male (loved dancing) with recent history of mild TBI (s/p fall) with early onset of Parkinson's disease presenting with "vicious pain and headaches." that keeps him up at night. He was losing his ambulatory skills. He was afraid of walking because he feared falling again. He was losing his compensatory skills he had had learned following his TBI. "I have had it, doc!"
- + Tried on numerous agents: narcotics, and benzodiazepines and Depakote.
- + Tapered him off those meds and started him on a TCA. He developed dry mouth. Stopped it and started him on Lyrica dosed three times a day. Biofeedback/CBT, PT & OT. Music therapy.
- + Doing well. Stable.

Central Pain Syndrome Bibliography

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+Questions?

